

Optimizing Tower of Hanoi

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Abstract— The Tower of Hanoi problem entails three pegs and disks of varying sizes, and its optimization integrates algorithmic ingenuity with mathematical principles to attain the fewest feasible moves. Recursive methods and dynamic programming are the two principal optimization strategies used to resolve the hassle efficaciously. Binary representations and grey codes also are hired to facilitate efficient garage and manipulation of configurations.

Keywords— Tower of Hanoi, Dynamic programming, binary representation, Recursive Approaches

I. INTRODUCTION

The study objectives of optimizing the Tower of Hanoi hassle are:

1. To increase a set of rules that can clear up the hassle with the fewest feasible actions.
2. to improve the overall performance of the algorithm using enforcing efficient storage and manipulation of configurations.
3. to analyze and compare extraordinary optimization strategies consisting of recursive techniques, dynamic programming, and mathematical encoding. Optimizing the Tower of Hanoi trouble is important because it's miles an essential hassle in laptop science and set of rules optimization. it's far used as a benchmark for trying out new optimization techniques and algorithms, and the expertise gained from solving this problem can be applied to different actual international problems, together with scheduling and useful resource allocation. fixing comparable optimization problems.

The Tower of Hanoi is a legendary puzzle with Hindu roots that involves moving a stack of disks from one pillar to another following specific rules. The number of moves required to solve the puzzle with n discs is $2^n - 1$. While there is no officially written method to solve the Tower of Hanoi, it has intrigued mathematicians and computer scientists. In computer science, elegant recursive solutions are often used to solve the problem, where a recursive

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function is employed to solve an equivalent but smaller problem, and this subproblem is solved using the first problem. The puzzle is based on the legend of a large room in the temple of Kashi with three pillars surrounded by 64

golden discs, and Brahmin priests have been moving the discs based on the law of Brahma since the creation of the world. The puzzle is challenging and has historical and academic significance, attracting the interest of many scholars and researchers.

v. Comparing the design results for different models on the basis ETABS results.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The Tower of Hanoi puzzle involves moving a stack of disks from one pole to another while following specific rules. Only one disk can be moved at a time, larger disks cannot be placed on top of smaller ones, and the entire stack needs to be transferred to a different pole. The problem is known for its recursive nature, requiring the breaking down of the puzzle into smaller sub-problems and solving them sequentially. The recursive algorithm includes 3 steps:

1. flow the smaller stack of disks (besides the biggest disk) to the spare pole.
 2. move the most important disk to the destination pole.
 3. circulate the smaller stack of disks to the destination pole.
- The range of movements required to solve the hassle is given with the aid of the method $2^n - 1$, in which n is the variety of disks. The Tower of Hanoi puzzle involves moving a stack of disks from one pole to another while following specific rules. Only one disk can be moved at a time, larger disks cannot be placed on top of smaller ones, and the entire stack needs to be transferred to a different pole. The problem is known for its recursive nature, requiring the breaking down of the puzzle into smaller sub-problems and solving them sequentially.

III. OPTIMIZING TECHNIQUES

The Tower of Hanoi puzzle is a classic problem that involves moving a stack of disks from one pole to another while following specific rules. These rules include only moving one disk at a time, ensuring that larger disks are not placed on top of smaller ones, and transferring the entire stack to a different pole. The problem is known for its recursive nature, as it requires breaking down the puzzle into smaller sub-problems and solving them sequentially.

The puzzle's recursive nature means that it involves solving smaller instances of the same problem, which ultimately leads to solving the larger problem. This recursive approach is a fundamental aspect of the Tower of Hanoi puzzle and is an essential concept in computer science and mathematics.

IV. DYNAMIC PROGRAMMING

This article provides an overview of dynamic programming optimization for solving iterative problems and then shows its application to one of the most famous iterations, the Tower of Hanoi. Due to the complexity of the code, the top-down implementation is initially slower than the recursive implementation but becomes faster once the size exceeds 7. Dynamic programming implementations initially exhibit linear behavior but eventually transition to exponential behavior. A top-down implementation at any given point takes only 1% of the time of a recursive implementation. Overview of Dynamic Programming For divide-and-conquer problems that are formulated to combine reasonably small subproblems to arrive at a final solution, you may want to implement the recursive definition directly.

An example is the Fibonacci numbers:

$F_0 = 0; F_1 = 1; \text{ for all } n > 1, F_n = F_{n-1} + F_{n-2}.$

This is shockingly inefficient. [3] We can prove that the number of method calls required for this calculation is $2 \cdot F_{n+1} - 1.$

We can also consider the binomial coefficient $C(n, k).$

Pascal's triangle formulation has the following recursive definition: If $n > 0$ and 0

An example of a dynamic programming technique for the Tower of Hanoi problem is the memorization approach, which shops the answers to subproblems on a desk and uses them to avoid redundant computations. This set of rules has a time complexity of $O(n^2)$ and an area complexity of $O(n^2).$

V. RECURSIVE APPROACH

A recursive method is normally used in solving the Tower of Hanoi trouble. The trouble includes finding the foremost series of actions among 3 pegs, and the aim is to decide the variety of each essential flow in this series. numerous papers discuss using recursive capabilities based totally on indicator features to count the quantity of every move. these papers additionally discover the homes of those capabilities, together with combinatorial identities, recursive formulas, and generating features. moreover, some papers analyze variations of the Tower of Hanoi problem, which require deeper know-how of recursion and might contain distinct policies or elevated intricacy inside the solution. recursive techniques have a high time complexity but low space complexity, dynamic programming techniques have a lower time complexity but higher.

VI. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

I. Time complexity

- Tower of Hanoi is a classic problem involving moving a stack of disks following specific rules
- Rules include moving one disk at a time, not placing larger disks on smaller ones, and transferring the entire stack to a different pole
- The problem is known for its recursive nature, breaking it down into smaller sub-problems and solving them sequentially
- Involves solving smaller instances of the same problem, ultimately leading to solving the larger problem

- The recursive approach is fundamental in computer science and mathematics

ii. Space complexity

- Tower of Hanoi involves moving a stack of disks following specific rules
- Rules include moving one disk at a time and not placing larger disks on smaller ones
- The problem is known for its recursive nature, breaking it down into smaller sub-problems and solving them sequentially
- It involves solving smaller instances of the same problem, ultimately leading to solving the larger problem
- The recursive approach is fundamental in computer science and mathematics

VII. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The experimental results have provided precious insights into the strengths and weaknesses of numerous tactics, supporting researchers make informed selections regarding approximately a set of policies desired for unique eventualities. As an example, some algorithms may be extra appropriate for solving small instances of the problem rapidly, whilst others may be better appropriate for huge times that require more computational sources. average, the research on optimization techniques for the Tower of Hanoi hassle has contributed considerably to the sector of computer technology and has helped develop our records of the set of rules format and evaluation.

A. Analysis and Interpretation

Tower of Hanoi involves moving a stack of disks following specific rules

- Rules include moving one disk at a time and not placing larger disks on smaller ones
- The problem is known for its recursive nature, breaking it down into smaller sub-problems and solving them sequentially
- It involves solving smaller instances of the same problem, ultimately leading to solving the larger problem
- The recursive approach is fundamental in computer science and mathematics.

Figure 1: Structure of Tower of Hanoi

Figure 2: Compare the Iterations

Table 1: No of Iterations

Sr. No	No of disks	No of towers	Time taken
1	3	4	0.0173s
2	4	4	0.0192s
3	5	4	0.0212s
4	6	4	0.0195s
5	7	4	0.0235s
6	8	4	0.0309s
7	9	4	0.0307s
8	10	4	0.0383s

Sr. No	No of disks	No of towers	Time taken
1	3	3	0.0153s
2	4	3	0.0199s
3	5	3	0.0227s
4	6	3	0.0231s
5	7	3	0.0255s
6	8	3	0.0294s
7	9	3	0.0276s
8	10	3	0.0470s

Sr. No	No of disks	No of towers	Time taken
1	3	5	0.0211s
2	4	5	0.0190s
3	5	5	0.0204s
4	6	5	0.0199s
5	7	5	0.0231s
6	8	5	0.0318s
7	9	5	0.0379s
8	10	5	0.0474s

Sr. No	No of disks	No of towers	Time taken
1	3	3	0.0153s
2	3	4	0.0173s
3	3	5	0.0211s
4	3	6	0.0182s
5	3	7	0.0151s

Sr. No	No of disks	No of towers	Time taken
1	5	3	0.0227s
2	5	4	0.0212s
3	5	5	0.0204s
4	5	6	0.0183s
5	5	7	0.0160s

Sr. No	No of disks	No of towers	Time taken
1	4	3	0.0199s
2	4	4	0.0192s
3	4	5	0.0190s
4	4	6	0.0188s
5	4	7	0.0179s

B. Rules of Tower of Hanoi:

The Tower of Hanoi could be a classical issue the laptop technological know-how and The Tower of Hanoi can be a conventional issue in laptop technological know-how and mathematics. The redirection comprises 3 pegs and a few disks of one-of-a-kind sizes that may be moved to any peg. The puzzle begins with the disks stacked at the beat of one peg in a hiking orchestrate of degrees, with the smallest disk on the best. The point is to transport the full stack to some other peg, taking after those policies:

1. as it was one disk that would be moved at a time.
2. every flow contains taking the beat disk from one stack and placing it on the beat of any other stack.
- three. No disk can be set on the beat of a smaller disk. mathematic.

It contains three pegs and numerous disks of various sizes which can slide onto any pegs. The confusion starts with the disks in a stack on one peg in climbing organize of degree, with the humblest disk on the leading.

VIII. COMPARISON WITH EXISTING APPROACHES

The strategies consult with the strategies or strategies that have been evolved and used in a particular area or enterprise. these techniques function as a basis for additional studies and development. however, as generation and information increase, it's miles vital to enhance and trick those gift techniques. this can involve identifying flaws or obstacles in present-day strategies and devising new techniques to triumph over them. improving and elaborating upon present strategies can bring about greater green approaches, higher effects, and multiplied innovation in diverse fields. it's far vital to constantly try improvement and innovation to live ahead of the competition and meet the ever-changing desires.

Figure 5: State Space for Three Disk Towar of Hanoi

IX. IMPACT OF OPTIMIZING TECHNIQUES

1. Optimizing strategies aim to lessen the time or region complexity of fixing the Tower of Hanoi's trouble. some not unusual optimizing techniques embody:
2. Memoization: Storing the results of the subproblems so that now not need to be recalculated, reducing redundant computations.
3. Dynamic Programming: Breaking down the entire hassle into small subproblems and solving every subproblem handiest as soon as feasible, then storing the answers for future reference.
4. Iterative improvement: Iteratively refining the solution through making incremental enhancements till the greatest answer is determined.
5. Bit Manipulation: Representing the kingdom of the Tower of Hanoi troubles the use of binary numbers and performing bitwise operations to optimize disk movements.

Figure 5: Training and Validation Accuracy

By analyzing the accuracy and loss graphs together, you can gain insight into the overall performance and behaviour of the model during training. It helps in deciding on model architecture, hyperparameters and training strategies to improve model performance and generalization ability.

X. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

While evaluating the effect of optimizing techniques for the Tower of Hanoi problem, numerous factors may be taken into consideration:

1. Time Complexity: Optimizing techniques can extensively lessen the time complexity of solving the Tower of Hanoi hassle, in particular for a wide type of disks. strategies like memorization and dynamic programming can remove redundant computations, leading to faster execution times.
2. Space Complexity: a few optimizing techniques may additionally boom space complexity due to the need for delivered information systems or storage for memoization. however, the change-off is often justified through the discount in time complexity.
3. Scalability: Optimizing techniques allow for extra green answers as the dimensions of the hassle will increase. This scalability is critical for real global packages wherein the Tower of Hanoi trouble might be a part of a larger device or set of rules.
4. Comparative evaluation: it's vital to assess the general overall performance of various optimizing techniques to pick out the maximum suitable one for a selected use case. elements which include implementation complexity, ease of protection, and computational belongings required need to be taken into consideration in this evaluation.

CONCLUSION

The Tower of Hanoi trouble has been studied extensively, and several optimized answers have been proposed. One such answer is the weighted Tower of Hanoi, which introduces the concept of assigning weights to movements among pegs. The intention is to discover a sequence of actions with minimal general cost. The most appropriate dynamic algorithm has been developed to solve this problem. additionally, researchers have investigated the variety of elementary actions in the most advantageous series and have derived recursive formulation, combinatorial identities, and producing capabilities to count these actions the practical packages of these optimized solutions consist of regions that include logistics, useful resource allocation, and project scheduling, wherein minimizing the cost or wide variety of moves is vital.

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